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A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON NON ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is becoming one of the most prominent causes of liver disease worldwide. Though NAFLD is increasingly prevalent in the Indian population, knowledge regarding the burden, risk factors, presentation and etiology of NAFLD is limited. Since last 2 decades there is a higher prevalence of obesity, Type 2 DM, Dyslipidemia, HTN, Insulin Resistance in Indian population with increased likelihood of these risk factors, there is a chance of greater prevalence of NAFLD. This study aims to study clinical profile and associated risk factors in patients with NAFLD. Our study was conducted over a period of 8 months in Department of Gastroenterology in a private clinic of Telangana region. A total of 324 patients diagnosed with NAFLD by ultrasonography were enrolled in the study. Prevalence was seen higher in male than female, more in urban population than rural and higher in 31-50 year age group. Mean age group was 44.20 years. Pain in abdomen was the most common clinical presentation. Risk factors were observed in [67.2%] patients and was more prevalent in 41-60 years age group. The most prevalent risk factor is HTN > Obesity > DM. 87% of patients had Grade I fatty liver. The study concludes that there is higher prevalence of risk factors in NAFLD patients. Thus there is a need for creating awareness regarding the disease and risk factors in general population for early detection and treatment.

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INTRODUCTION

NAFLD [Non Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease] comprises of spectrum of liver clinicopathological conditions ranging from pure fatty steatosis [Fatty infiltration in > 5 % Hepatocytes] without inflammation to the [NASH] Non alcoholic Steatohepatitis which may progress to cirrhosis, liver failure and Hepatocellular carcinoma. It is characterized by excessive fat accumulation in the liver parenchyma of patients who have no history of alcohol abuse (< 20 g per day in men and < 10 g in women) [1]. NAFLD is the most common liver disease in the western world. Even in India NAFLD is emerging as an important cause of liver disease [2]. Prevalence varies, depending on the population of the study and using diagnostic criteria. It is characterized by insulin resistance and mitochondrial dysfunction. Indeed, there is a gradual increase in the severity of insulin resistance in the range of NAFLD which may contribute to the evolution of liver damage. Diabetes, dyslipidemia, hypertension and CVD coexist more frequently in individuals with NAFLD [1]. NAFLD was recognized during 1950 by Zelman and Westwater and Fainer [2]. In the United States, the prevalence of NAFLD varies between 10 % and 35 %. [3]. In India the epidemiological studies suggest prevalence of NAFLD around 9 % to 35 % of general population. With higher prevalence in those with overweight or obesity and in those with diabetes or prediabetes. Urbanization and associated changes, such as sedentary life style and rich fat diet, and a higher inherited tendency for diabetes mellitus makes Indians more prone to metabolic syndrome or insulin resistance and its manifestations such as NAFLD [2]. Primary causes of NAFLD are obesity, type II diabetes, and the metabolic syndrome including dyslipidemia and hypertension. Secondary causes of NAFLD are drugs, surgery, total parenteral nutrition, etc [4]. NAFLD is largely asymptomatic although fatigue and right upper quadrant abdominal pain are reported by a proportion of patients [5]. NAFLD is suspected by identifying commonly associated risk factors, finding steatosis on imaging, and excluding other causes of liver disease [6]. Ultrasonography is the most widely used method but is relatively insensitive, as it can detect steatosis only when liver fat content exceeds 33% [7].

GRADING OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER ON ULTRASONOGRAPHY:

Grade I (mild):

Minimal diffuse increase in the fine echoes.

Grade II (moderate):

Moderate diffuse increase in the fine echoes. Slightly impaired visualization of the intrahepatic vessels and diaphragm. Liver appears bright compared to the cortex of the kidney. Normal visualization of diaphragm and intrahepatic vessel borders.

Grade III (severe):

Marked increase in the fine echoes. Poor or no visualisation of intrahepatic vessels and diaphragm and poor penetration of the posterior, segment of the right lobe of the liver.

Though liver biopsy is the gold standard method for diagnosis of NAFLD, Ultrasonography is non-invasive, simple tool, can be used for the early detection of NAFLD in asymptomatic patients [8]. The aim of study was to assess clinical profile and associated risk factors in patients with NAFLD.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY SITE:

A prospective observational study was conducted at gastro clinic in Warangal region for a period of 8 months from February 2017 to September 2017. Patients were selected based on inclusion criteria. The data was collected in a pre-designed data collection form.

STUDY DESIGN:

Prospective observational study.

STUDY PERIOD:

This study was carried out for a period of 8 months.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

All people diagnosed with Non Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease by abdominal ultrasonography.

Patients with NAFLD and comorbid conditions like HTN and DM.

Both genders.

Patients of age > 20 years.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patient with history of alcohol intake of more than 20g/day in males and more than 10g/day in females.

Patients with history of jaundice or HBs Ag positive

Patients with history of intake of hepatotoxic drugs

Patients with secondary causes of NAFLD

Patients of age < 20 years

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS:

Patient data was collected with the consent of patient or care taker to obtain details such as– age, sex, height, weight, BMI; Clinical presentation of patient; comorbid conditions – hypertension, diabetes mellitus, CAD, lung disorders, bone problems; Risk factors – smoking, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism, Poly cystic ovarian syndrome, obesity. Data from abdominal ultrasonography was also collected. All the above mentioned parameters for each patient were entered in data collection form. Data collected was entered in to Microsoft Excel 2007 database for analysis.

ETHICAL COMMITTEE APPROVAL:

The protocol of the study was approved by Institutional Ethical Committee of Care College of Pharmacy, Warangal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NAFLD is the most common cause of liver disease, representing over 75 % of the chronic liver disease in United States [9]. The prevalence of fatty liver increases with age in adults, and while the exact incidence of the disease is unknown [10]. Results from prevalence studies done internationally have varied widely, with recent studies done in Japan and England indicating the prevalence of the disease has nearly doubled over the last twenty years [11]. NAFLD is rising in the Asia-Pacific region mainly due to the lifestyles change i.e., increasing fat in the diet, less physical activity, increasing prevalence of type 2 diabetes [12].

Among 324 patients enrolled in our study, gender wise classification showed that male are predominant [57.7%] when compared to female [42.29 %]. Gender based classification in the study is comparable to studies done by Singh et al. [13] in which out of 464 patients 359 were males & 102 were females, Amarapurkar et al. [14] Prevalence was higher in males than females. Some old studies reported that women were at higher risk for NAFLD, but these studies were not population based and were subject to potential ascertainment Bias [15].

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to age and gender.

Age in years	Male	Percentage of males	Female	Percentage of females	Total no.of patients	Percentage
21-30	34	10.19 %	13	4 %	46	14.19 %
31-40	70	21.6 %	24	7.4 %	94	29 %
41-50	43	13 %	44	13.64 %	86	26.54 %
51-60	26	8 %	34	10.82 %	61	18.82 %
61-70	12	3.7 %	15	4.94 %	28	8.64 %
71-80	5	1.5 %	4	1.3 %	9	2.80 %

The study population was divided in to various groups according to their age and gender. Prevalence was seen more in the age groups of 31- 50 years. In male more prevalence seen in 31-40 years age group where as in female more prevalence seen in 41-50 years age group. In the present study mean age group is 44.20 years, Similar results were found in the study conducted by Anurag et al. [16], Gaharwar et al. [17], Majumdar et al. [18], Singh et al. [13] were mean age group was [50.75] years, [49. 20] years, [54.4 ± 10.6] years, [42.15 ± 10.54] years respectively. In another study done by Amarapurkar et al. [19] more prevalence was seen in age group of 40 to 60 years.

In the present study 56.2% of patients are from urban area then followed by rural area [43.8 %] this is comparable to a study done by Kumar et al. [20] in 160 patients the prevalence was higher in urban patients [58.72 %] than the rural patients [31.25 %].

In the study population majority of patients are on mixed diet accounting for [92.3 %] then followed by vegetarian [7.7 %]. In the present study majority of patients were consuming diet rich in carbohydrate, high fat, fried food, sweets, coffee and tea daily which is comparable to study done by Singh et al. [13] where patients with NAFLD consumed red meat, spicy food, fried food and tea.

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to occupation.

NAFLD was more prevalent in unemployed patients [34 %]. In present study [28.4 %] of patients with NAFLD had sedentary life style which is comparable to study which is done by Singh et al. [13] where majority of patients had sedentary life style developed NAFLD. Sedentary life can lead to insulin resistance which is a major risk factor for NAFLD.

Figure 2: Clinical presentation of patients with NAFLD.

NAFLD is largely asymptomatic although fatigue and right upper quadrant abdominal pain are reported by a proportion of patients [5]. In our study 62 % of patients complained of abdominal pain is which is close 55.7% seen in another study [17].

Figure 3: Patients with risk factors and without risk factors.

Of 324 patients, risk factors were found in 218 [67.2 %] patients. Of these 218 patients with risk factors majority of patients are from 41-60 years age group. In our study 67.2 % of the patients presented with risk factors ≥ 1 , hence it is possible that risk factors may gradually lead to NAFLD by slowly altering hepatic metabolism.

Figure 4: Prevalence of risk factors.

Commonly seen comorbid conditions in our study were HTN > Obesity > DM > Hyperlipidaemia. In a study done by Gaharwar et al. [17] HTN, Obesity, DM, Hypercholestromaemia, Hypertriglyceridaemia, were seen in [35.72 %] [45.7 %] [32.86 %] [45.71 %] [67.14 %] patients respectively. In a study done Anurag et al. [16] of 85 patients diagnosed with NAFLD; HTN, DM, metabolic syndrome was seen [38.82 %] [48.24 %] [36.47 %] patients respectively. In a study done by Radu C, et al. [23] of 604 cases with NAFLD obesity, DM, HTN, hypertriglyceridaemia was seen in 88.41 %, 68.87 %, 62.58 %, 55.79 % patients respectively. Although similar pattern was seen in our study incidence percentage varied. Hypothyroidism and PCOS are emerging as conditions associated with NAFLD [24] were also observed in our study. Hypothyroidism was observed in 21 patients, PCOS was observed in 11 patients. Prevalence of NAFLD within the PCOS population is now estimated to be anywhere between 15 % and 55 %, depending on the diagnostic index used for both NAFLD and PCOS.

Table 2: Age group verses risk factor.

Age group	DM	HTN	Obesity	PCOS	Hypothyroidism	Hyperlipidemia	Total
21-30	-	-	2	1	1	-	4
31-40	6	11	20	5	6	1	49
41-50	18	28	38	3	5	3	95
51-60	22	20	18	1	4	1	66
61-70	11	21	4	1	4	-	41
71-80	5	7	-	-	1	-	13
Total	62	87	82	11	21	5	268

The prevalence of various risk factors are estimated in different age group and it is seen from observations that most affected age group with risk factors are between 41-60 years.

Figure 5: Distribution of patients according to grade of NAFLD.

In our study, [87 %] of patients had grade I fatty liver, grade II [9.56 %], grade III [3.39 %] which is comparable to studies conducted by Majumdar et al. [18] in which, of 176 patients 74.1 % had grade I, 22.2 % had grade II, 1 % had grade III fatty liver and Anurag et al. [16] out of 70 patients with NAFLD grade I, II, III seen respectively in 51 [72.85 %], 24 [34.28 %], 5 [7 %] patients. Similar pattern is seen in our study. In the present study as 87 % of patients were of grade I fatty liver which indicates that there is a great scope for early treatment and recovery.

Sedentary life style and improper diet leading to obesity is the major avoidable risk factor which can be avoided by counselling but in our study we observed that only 13% patients were recommended for lifestyle modifications. Hence there is a necessity of clinical pharmacist presence in department of gastroenterology. By creating awareness about disease, patient counselling and understanding the gravity of risk factors a pharmacist can play a vital role in preventing the wide spread of NAFLD.

CONCLUSION

NAFLD is most common cause of liver diseases and its importance is rising in the Asia-pacific region due to lifestyle changes. Consumption of saturated fats and added sugars are the major cause of concern. Risk factors like HTN, DM obesity and hyperlipidemia are highly prevalent in our study population. Conditions with emerging association with NAFLD such as hypothyroidism and PCOS are also seen in our study population.. Based on our study results majority of patients were of grade I fatty liver which indicates a great scope for early treatment and recovery. Therefore we recommend implementation of lifestyle modification (exercise, diet), creating awareness regarding the disease and risk factors in general population helps in early detection and treatment of disease which can be effectively done by clinical pharmacist.

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